

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

WP5 – Development of the hackAIR platform

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

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Table of Contents

Glossary	5
1 Executive summary	6
2 From DoA to system architecture	6
3 hackAIR Platform Architecture	7
3.1 General Guidelines for the hackAIR Platform	8
3.1.1 User Interface design in the hackAIR Platform	8
3.1.2 Localization	8
3.1.3 Security	9
3.2 High-level Architecture	10
3.2.1 Data layer	11
3.2.1.1 Data entities	11
3.2.1.2 Semantically enriched information	12
3.2.2 Business Logic layer	12
3.2.3 Application layer	14
3.3 Information flow	14
3.4 Integration framework	16
4 hackAIR Modules Architecture & API	16
4.1 Modules Architecture	16
4.1.1 Social Media Mining	16
4.1.2 Open Data Crawling	17
4.1.3 Image Analysis	18
4.1.1 Problem Description	19
4.1.2 Recommendations and Decision Support	20
4.1.3 Knowledge Base	20
4.1.4 Data Retrieval	21
4.1.5 Data Fusion	22
4.1.6 Gamification and Reputation System	23
4.2 REST API	25
4.2.1 HTTP Verbs	25
4.2.2 HTTP Response Status Codes	25
4.2.3 Authentication	26
4.2.4 Endpoints	26
5 Software & Hardware Specifications	27

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

5.1 Hardware Specifications	27
5.2 Software Specifications.....	27
6 hackAIR Implementation Approach	28
6.1 Software Development Methodology	28
6.2 Technical Documentation Management	30
6.3 Source Code Repository Management	30
6.4 Issue Tracking Management & Reporting.....	31
6.5 Deployment Methodology.....	31
7 Testing Methodology.....	31
7.1 Testing Methodology.....	31
7.2 API & Integration Testing.....	32
7.3 User Interface Testing.....	32
7.4 Security Testing	32
7.5 User Acceptance Testing (UAT)	32
8 Conclusions.....	33
References.....	34
Appendix I – List of User stories	35

Table of Figures

Figure 1: hackAIR high level architecture	11
Figure 2: Data retrieval from all sources & insertion to the database	15
Figure 3: Data retrieval from the database to be displayed on the web/mobile apps.	15
Figure 4 Social media mining module architecture	17
Figure 5: Open data crawling module architecture	18
Figure 6: Image analysis module architecture	19
Figure 7: Knowledge base module architecture	21
Figure 8: Data retrieval module architecture	22
Figure 9: Data fusion architecture	23
Figure 10: Gamification & Reputation System’s architecture.....	24
Figure 11: Scrum in a picture	29
Figure 12: Swagger UI.....	30

Glossary

Abbreviation/Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
KB	Knowledge Base
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RWD	Responsive Web Design
UI	User Interface

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the architecture design of the hackAIR platform and its subcomponents and defines the framework for their integration into the core platform. More specifically, the deliverable covers the following topics:

- ♥ The general architecture of the hackAIR platform
- ♥ The architecture of the platform's subcomponents
- ♥ The hardware and software specifications
- ♥ The implementation approach that will be followed in hackAIR, including the methodologies for software development, technical documentation management, source code repository management and deployment.
- ♥ The methodology and tools that will be used for testing the platform from various perspectives such as API & integration, User Interface, Security and User Acceptance testing.

2 From DoA to system architecture

During the first 7 months of the project, our main focus was to gather all the necessary information in order to conclude on the architecture and integration framework as well as help in the gathering of user requirements.

Our first step in gathering the technical requirements was to create a document with specific questions regarding the different components of the system that would give us a starting point for further discussions. This document, called a "component card", was shared with all technical partners, i.e. DRAXIS, NILU, CERTH, DUTH and the TEI of Athens, who were asked to complete one for each component they were responsible for. After we received that input, we set up skype calls and face to face meetings in order to discuss details, clarify blurry points and evolve the idea of the hackAIR system into something that would form the final backbone of the hackAIR platform.

Based on the information we got from the component cards, we created a first draft of the system architecture. Further discussions took place in order to take the final decisions regarding the hackAIR architecture.

Very important to that process was the interaction with the partner responsible for the user requirements in order to be constantly aware of the functionalities desired by the users. On that front, we had regular communication with VUB in order to get informed about the process and give our feedback. Specifically, regarding the gamification aspect of the application, we contacted gamification experts in order to get professional help. However, in a common decision with VUB, we decided not to include them at the current stage. Because of the way the first round of interviews with the end users was set up, their incorporation to the project would be problematic.

During this period decisions on the following topics were taken, which are described in the following chapters:

- ♥ Overall architecture of the system
- ♥ Integration framework
- ♥ Communication interfaces
- ♥ Software development methodology
- ♥ Issue tracking and software development tools
- ♥ Technical documentation tools
- ♥ Technologies to be used
- ♥ Server requirements
- ♥ Testing methodology
- ♥ Delineation of key concepts of the application

3 hackAIR Platform Architecture

The hackAIR open platform will enable communities of citizens to easily set up air quality monitoring networks and engage their members in measuring and publishing outdoor air pollution levels, leveraging the power of social networks, mobile and open hardware technologies and engagement strategies.

The platform will allow the collection, fusion and visualization of air quality data from various data sources, including publicly available data and contributions from the hackAIR community.

Publicly available data may come from:

- 📍 measurements by existing air quality stations and open data
- 📍 geo-tagged and time-stamped sky-depicting images posted through social media platforms
- 📍 sky-depicting images available from web cameras

Contributions from the community may include:

- 📍 sky-depicting images captured by users of the hackAIR application
- 📍 measurements submitted through low-cost open hardware devices (users will be given instructions on how to set them up):
 - **Arduino device:** This will provide an easy way for people interested or getting started with do-it-yourself electronics to use an assortment of commercially available, low-cost air quality sensors. The process will be well documented to help experienced “hackers” modify and extend it while remaining simple enough to allow newbie users to make their own measurements at home
 - **Air Quality Beacon device:** The Air Quality Beacon is a small device positioned outdoors with an attached sensor. The BLEAir (Bluetooth Low Energy Beacon) node will acquire data values from the attached sensor and it will transmit (through Bluetooth) to a nearby smartphone the value of PM particles in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.
 - **Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) device:** In this case the measurements will be acquired by pumping air from the free environment and guiding it through a filter. The user will have to take high-resolution photos of the filter (before and after).

The data available from the above sources will be processed by the hackAIR platform and merged through a data fusion algorithm to provide value-added and personalized information on air quality to the platform’s users.

The hackAIR platform will be available to citizens through a web and a mobile application and also the Community Portal. The web application will allow users to collect, publish and view air quality data and will also provide configuration instructions on how communities can create their own community portal, by installing the hackAIR application and customizing it according to their needs. The mobile application (available in Android and iOS) will allow citizens to contribute air quality data by uploading sky-depicting images and measurements through low-cost hardware devices, access air quality information and receive personalized alerts and recommendations. These applications (web, mobile, community portal) will retrieve and provide information to the core hackAIR platform through a RESTful API.

This chapter describes the architecture of the hackAIR platform. As an introduction, we present the general guidelines that will be followed for the design and development of the platform. Next, we present the high-level architecture, the flow of information between its subcomponents and the integration framework that will bring these subcomponents under the core hackAIR platform.

3.1 General Guidelines for the hackAIR Platform

This section introduces general guidelines for the hackAIR Platform including web and mobile user interface guidelines, localization in the platform and security aspects.

3.1.1 User Interface design in the hackAIR Platform

As far as the hackAIR web app's UI is concerned, it will be designed following the common guidelines for usability, accessibility and efficiency. Furthermore, the web UI will follow the principles of Responsive Web Design (RWD), an approach to web design that suggests that design and development should respond to the user's behavior and environment based on screen size, platform and orientation. This approach provides an optimal viewing experience — ease of reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling — across a wide range of devices (from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones). The web app UI will be developed using the Angular JS¹ framework, HTML5 and CSS3.

The hackAIR app's mobile UI will vary depending on the device's operating system and characteristics (screen resolution etc.). Moreover, the mobile UI design will incorporate some of the recommended style guides from Apple (iOS) and Google (Android). The mobile apps will be developed using Ionic², an open-source framework which is based on Angular JS and allows building modern and interactive mobile apps for all available platforms (hybrid).

3.1.2 Localization

The hackAIR platform will be tested in two pilot countries: Germany and Norway. In order for the pilots to run successfully, the platform needs to be localized in three different languages: English, German and Norwegian. Additional languages may be required after the end of the project, in the framework of exploitation activities. Thus, the platform needs to provide a localization mechanism that will allow the translation of local resources (texts) to be easy and maintainable. All resources that need to be translated will be stored in files separate for each language and will be queried through the localization mechanism depending on the language that the user has selected. In the initial phase of the platform's development the resources will be available in English only. When the development reaches a mature level, all resources will be translated to the rest of the languages and the translations will be integrated to the hackAIR platform. Each language will be accessible through a different URL in the hackAIR web app, as shown below:

- <http://hackair.eu> - English
- <http://hackair.eu/de> - German
- <http://hackair.eu/no> - Norwegian

The same applies to the mobile app that will also be translated in the three languages mentioned above. The option to change the language will be available through the settings of the application.

¹ <https://angularjs.org/>

² <http://ionicframework.com/>

3.1.3 Security

The purpose of this section is to define the security policies and rules that help ensure the security and availability of the hackAIR platform and also the confidentiality, integrity and availability of the data captured, stored and used in hackAIR. The security policies and rules include the following:

Authentication / Authorisation

Only the authorised user can have access to specific information (for example the user profile can be viewed only by the person who owns the account).

Cross-site scripting

Cross-Site Scripting (XSS)³ attacks are a type of injection, in which malicious scripts are injected into otherwise benign and trusted web sites. XSS attacks occur when an attacker uses a web application to send malicious code, generally in the form of a browser side script, to a different end user. The end user's browser has no way to know that the script should not be trusted, and will execute the script. Because it thinks the script came from a trusted source, the malicious script can access any cookies, session tokens, or other sensitive information retained by the browser and used with that site.

What we will do to protect hackAIR

Our application will be using Laravel's XSS protection filters and middleware to filter html output.

How to test it

For every field that consists users' input that will be displayed on screen, we will be entering malicious scripts to check that the malicious act is prohibited and the script is only displayed as text.

SQL injection

A SQL injection attack⁴ consists of insertion or "injection" of a SQL query via the input data from the client to the application. A successful SQL injection exploit can read sensitive data from the database, modify database data, execute administration operations on the database and so on. The vulnerability happens when user input is not filtered for string literal escape characters used in SQL statements. SQL commands are thus injected from the web form into the database of an application (like queries).

What we will do to protect hackAIR

Our web and mobile application will only talk to the database (read, write, modify) through the system's API. The API will filter user's input for malicious scripts and ensure the request comes from an authorized user. All suspicious actions will be logged and an email will be sent to the technical team.

How to test it

Enter some malicious sql scripts in places where the user enters free text and make sure these scripts are not executed.

Error cases- Revealing of sensitive information

³ [https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Cross-site_Scripting_\(XSS\)](https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Cross-site_Scripting_(XSS))

⁴ https://www.owasp.org/index.php/SQL_Injection

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

As part of testing the web application, all commonly used error codes will be tested (400 Bad request, 401 Unauthorized, 403 forbidden, 404 not found, 500 Internal server error) in order to ensure that the errors returned reveal no sensitive information.

Insecure direct object reference

Insecure Direct Object References⁵ allow attackers to bypass authorization and access resources directly by modifying the value of a parameter used to directly point to an object. Such resources can be database entries belonging to other users, files in the system, and more. This is caused by the fact that the application takes user supplied input and uses it to retrieve an object without performing sufficient authorization checks

What we will do to protect hackAIR

We will be preventing insecure direct object reference by:

- Enforcing access control to ensure the user is authorized for the requested object.
- Enforce validation on both client and server side in order to avoid the use of proxy tools that can bypass client side validation.
- Using per user or session indirect object references: This approach can be used to prevent attackers from directly targeting unauthorized resources. For example, use a drop down list of resources authorized instead of database key for the current user to limit the user input. The application has to map the per-user indirect reference back to the actual database key on the server

How to test it⁶

Whenever a URL contains an id/string etc. that corresponds to a user's specific resources we will be manually testing that changing the id cannot lead to accessing another users resources.

Access level control

We will always ensure that only the right users have access to specific areas of the application (for example admin area can only be accessed by authorised admins of the system)

3.2 High-level Architecture

The hackAIR platform's architecture is composed of the following three layers as shown in Figure 1: Data, Business Logic and Application layers. The communication between these layers is bi-directional and always passes through the business logic layer. The communication between the Application and the Business logic layers is handled through a RESTful API.

⁵ https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Top_10_2013-A4-Insecure_Direct_Object_References

⁶ [https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Testing_for_Insecure_Direct_Object_References_\(OTG-AUTHZ-004\)](https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Testing_for_Insecure_Direct_Object_References_(OTG-AUTHZ-004))

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Figure 1: hackAIR high level architecture

3.2.1 Data layer

The data layer includes the data persistence mechanisms that are responsible for storing and retrieving the data used by the hackAIR platform. It is comprised of a database for storing the basic hackAIR data entities and a Knowledge Base for storing semantically enriched information.

3.2.1.1 Data entities

The data entities currently identified in the hackAIR platform are the following:

User data

The users who register to the hackAIR platform will provide profile data such as contact information, location, open hardware sensors and system preferences, which will be saved in the hackAIR database.

Air quality data

Air quality data will be acquired from various sources, including:

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

📍 Photos

- geo-tagged and time-stamped images posted through social media platforms
- user-generated images, captured and submitted by the users of the hackAIR mobile app

📍 Measurements

- measurements by existing air quality stations and open data
- measurements submitted by citizens using low-cost open hardware devices

The air quality data, either acquired as raw measurements or extracted from photos, along with additional descriptive information such as user, location, timestamp, etc. will be stored in the hackAIR database.

3.2.1.2 Semantically enriched information

The hackAIR platform will also use semantics in order to be able to provide personalized recommendations and alerts. For this purpose, the hackAIR platform will include a separate repository that is more appropriate for storing semantic information. The repository will store the ontology along with the user related information including her profile (as retrieved from the Personalization module), the query that includes the activity performed, the place of interest etc. (as retrieved from the Problem Description Module), and the measurements related to the query (as retrieved from the Data Fusion Module).

3.2.2 Business Logic layer

The business logic layer will handle the requests coming from the application layer, by applying the business logic rules and replying securely with proper content to the client applications (web and mobile applications). In addition to that, it will receive measurements taken by the Arduino device through the API and route them to the appropriate module. Finally, the business-logic layer will communicate with external components including official websites, social media platforms and webcams in order to retrieve air quality data.

The business logic layer will include the various modules of the hackAIR platform, which may fall under the following three categories:

Data ingest

The main data ingest modules, responsible for acquiring data from various sources, are described below:

- 📍 **Social media mining module:** This module will collect geotagged images from social networks, which will then be processed by collective sensing techniques. The collection of additional air quality sources from social media will be investigated and will be supported by the module if deemed valuable.
- 📍 **Open data crawling module:** This module will deal with the discovery and profiling of environmental websites. Regarding the discovery part, a focused crawler and query formulation and expansion based on domain-specific terms (using ontologies and keyword spices) will be applied for finding websites with environmental measurements. A list of web sites will be discovered using the above techniques and then this list will be used by the platform.
- 📍 **Text mining module:** This module involves the extraction of environmental content from web sites and web services. In case of web services the format of the data is well defined and data can be retrieved by simple JSON/XML parsing. As far as web sites are concerned, information extraction will be based on the extraction and transformation of semi-structured web content, typically in HTML format, into structured data. This task typically involves acquiring the page content, processing it by parsing the HTML structure, and extracting the relevant information using regular expressions.

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

- 📌 **Webcams Data module:** This module will retrieve images from webcams from the following sources:
 - extraction of images found in web sites. These images are captured by webcams and uploaded in the sites in form of images.
 - use of existing webcam dataset like AMOS dataset⁷ and provide access to the images retrieved.

The retrieved images will then be processed by the Image Analysis Module.

Data processing

This part will include modules responsible for information transformation, processing and implementation of business rules and consists of the following:

- 📌 **Image analysis module:** This module will use image processing techniques for recognizing images with a “good” deal of sky and then locate the part of the image containing the sky.
- 📌 **Problem description module:** This module’s goal is to generate a description of the problem in PDL submitted by the user to the hackAIR platform, according to the information provided by the user via the user interface.
- 📌 **Recommendations and decision support module:** This module will read the data from the Knowledge Base (which contains the data from the Fusion service, the profile data, and the query data) and using reasoning techniques, it will provide recommendations to the end-user.
- 📌 **Quality Control module:** This module will be responsible for measurements data validation by determining the quality of the data that gets inserted to the database. It will exclude invalid measurements e.g. measurements that do not fit into a valid scale as well as measurements from sensors that are not operating properly (e.g. have an internal error).
- 📌 **Data fusion module:** The fusion module will use geostatistics to combine scattered point-based observations of air quality with spatially exhaustive output from a chemical transport model or a statistical air quality model. Through data fusion, value is added to the observations by spatially interpolating in a mathematically objective fashion, while value is added to the model by constraining it based on the observations.
- 📌 **Gamification and reputation system module:** This module will provide a game-like service to various parts of the application in order for them to allow their end users to gather points, earn badges or rewards as well as provide leaderboards, reputation systems and other user engagement elements. The reputation system part of the module will ensure the quality of data and will minimize risks of capture and manipulation, as competent users will also get motivation from having their contributions being recognized as valuable.

Data access

This part will include modules that will be responsible to communicate with the hackAIR platform’s database systems, like the ones listed below:

- 📌 **Data retrieval module:** This module will be responsible for the retrieval of the requested information (i.e. measurements of specific aspects) for the geographical area of interest and time/date.
- 📌 **Knowledge Base module:** The Knowledge Base module will support the access to the Knowledge Base on which the whole platform relies to provide user decision support. This service will provide, via the KB Access interface, access, manipulation and storage of ontologies (or ontology modules) stored in the Knowledge Base.

⁷ AMOS dataset, <http://amos.cse.wustl.edu/dataset>

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

The communication between the business logic and application layers as well as the communication between the various modules in the business logic layer will be performed via a RESTful API which will be accessible via the HTTP protocol. The RESTful API will cover actions like:

- ♥ User management, authentication, and authorization
- ♥ Air quality data management
- ♥ Alert notification production, according to user's preferences or actions
- ♥ Filter and serve information according to user's location and preferences

3.2.3 Application layer

The application layer will host the user's interaction interface. It will be available to the web and mobile applications and also the community portal. The applications provided through this layer will be developed using the Angular JS framework, HTML5 and CSS3. The mobile application will also be wrapped using the Ionic framework in order to provide all features required for the Android and iOS platforms. It will offer full end-user access to all hackAIR services. Users will not only consume data, but will also provide data like personal information and air quality estimations (through photos and air quality measurements coming from hardware devices).

The application layer will include the following modules that will be shared across the web and mobile apps:

- ♥ **AQ Visualization module:** This module will comprise a set of web widgets that will facilitate the communication of air quality measurements across space and time. It will support different means of conveying air quality measures: a) temporal view (e.g. timeline), b) spatial view (e.g. heatmap), and c) comparative view (e.g. city pollution leaderboard).
- ♥ **Communication module:** The communication module will act as a message board, allowing users to ask questions to the hackAIR community and receive feedback and help from other users. This could be either a discussion forum or a Q&A module (like Yahoo Answers, for example). Questions, comments etc. will be public to all members of the hackAIR community.
- ♥ **Profile management module:** This module will manage user profiles. User profiles can be created, written, deleted and queried. It will aggregate the user's personal information as well as the achievements from his interactions with the Gamification and reputation system module in order to build the user's online profile.
- ♥ **Personalization module:** The Personalization module will present personalized information to users. It will get the recommendation for the user from the Recommendations and decision support module and will create personalized alerts and suggestions for the user.

The mobile app will also include the following libraries in order to handle the communication with two of the hardware devices:

- ♥ **Air Quality Beacon:** A library which will receive the sensor measurements via Bluetooth and will send them to the hackAIR platform.
- ♥ **Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS):** A library that will estimate the air quality by comparing mobile phone photos, applying a computer vision algorithm and send the results to the hackAIR platform.

3.3 Information flow

The flow of information between the various modules of the hackAIR platform is presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Specifically, Figure 2 shows how the data are retrieved from the various sources (open data, social media platforms,

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

mobile app and user-developed sensors), processed, transformed and validated through various modules and finally inserted to the hackAIR database using a common format.

Figure 2: Data retrieval from all sources & insertion to the database.

Figure 3 shows how the data are retrieved from the database and are processed through various components before they are finally presented to the end users of the web and mobile apps.

Figure 3: Data retrieval from the database to be displayed on the web/mobile apps.

3.4 Integration framework

The hackAIR platform will follow the guidelines of Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) for the integration of all platform components. SOA is an architectural pattern in computer software design in which application components provide services to other components via a communications protocol, typically over a network. The principles of service-orientation are independent of any vendor, product or technology. Services are unassociated, loosely coupled units of functionality that are self-contained. Each service implements at least one action. This makes it possible to reuse the code in different ways throughout the application by changing only the way an individual service interoperates with other services that make up the application, versus making code changes to the service itself.

Furthermore, the hackAIR Platform will implement the REST Web Services design approach to sustain integration among subcomponents and other integrations like mobile devices. REST is the software architectural style of the World Wide Web. REST gives a coordinated set of constraints to the design of components in a distributed hypermedia system that can lead to a higher-performing and more maintainable architecture. RESTful systems typically, but not always, communicate over HTTP with the usual HTTP verbs.

All REST APIs of the hackAIR Platform and its subcomponents will be published online on the hackAIR web site and also via API links for specific components.

The various components will be integrated to the hackAIR platform in multiple iterations in order to produce the final version of the platform. After each iteration, integration testing will be performed by the development team in order to ensure that the integration was successful. In case problems are found during the integration, these will be resolved and tested again until all integration tests run without problems. In the end of this process, the components will be fully integrated to the core of the hackAIR platform, accompanied with the proper technical documentation that will be available to developers.

4 hackAIR Modules Architecture & API

4.1 Modules Architecture

4.1.1 Social Media Mining

This module will collect a variety of pertinent data sources from social media. It will focus on the collection of geotagged images, which will then be processed by collective sensing techniques. The collection of additional air quality sources from social media will be investigated and will be supported by the module if deemed valuable.

Inputs:

Set of locations of interest

Outputs:

Collected data in the form of images and associated metadata (location, time, tags, etc.).

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java.

Architecture:

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

The Social Media Mining Module (Figure 4) runs on a daily basis retrieving images from Flickr, saving their metadata (i.e. coordinates, timestamp, text related etc.) to a Mongo database. Then a REST API of the Image Analysis Module is called to process the retrieved images.

Figure 4 Social media mining module architecture

4.1.2 Open Data Crawling

This module deals with the discovery and profiling of environmental websites in the web.

Regarding the discovery part, a focused crawler and query formulation and expansion based on domain-specific terms (using ontologies and keyword spices) will be applied for finding websites with environmental measurements.

A list of web sites will be discovered using the above techniques and then this list will be used from the platform. So discovery is something done offline.

Inputs:

A set of web sites that provide environmental measurements using as start for the crawler

Outputs:

The list of web sites containing environmental measurements.

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java.

Architecture:

The component's architecture (Figure 5) combines results from a focused crawler, and a general purpose based domain search engine. More specifically, the modules' pipeline 1→2 reflects the procedure of discovering nodes by using a focused crawler; the pipeline 3→4 refers to the creation of domain specific queries which are fed into a general purpose search engine. The retrieved results are then post-processed in order to select nodes that contain specific types of information and extract them. Therefore, the retrieved websites pass sequentially through the following components: a page classification component (5) in which the web pages are classified as relevant based on their key-phrases of the web page, a crawling component (6) where each node that has been characterized as relevant previously in crawled in order to retrieve the rest webpages of the site, a storing component (7) where each of the

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

nodes (i.e. web pages) that has been identified is stored in a Mongo database, a filtering component (8) where the URLs are filtered manually and only the ones containing relevant information that can be extracted automatically are kept, and finally a web page information extraction component (9) that processes each page based on web page specific templated and stores the extracted information into a csv file.

Figure 5: Open data crawling module architecture

4.1.3 Image Analysis

This module will use image processing techniques for recognizing images with a “good” deal of sky and then locate the part of the image containing the sky.

Inputs:

Set of images

Outputs:

Image mask showing the part of the image with sky.

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java, C.

Architecture:

The Image Analysis Module is called by the Webcams Data Module, the Social Media Mining Module and the Mobile App Image Module in order to fetch and analyze the images provided. The results of the processing are stored in a Mongo Database. The architecture is presented in Figure 6.

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Figure 6: Image analysis module architecture

Communication interface:

The communication with the Image Analysis Module includes 2 core REST API endpoints and 1 optional. Specifically:

- ♥ (core): `{BASE_URL}/SingleImage/image=<Image URL>`: An HTTP GET method that provides as input a single image URL
- ♥ (core): `{BASE_URL}/MultipleImages/`: An HTTP POST method that provides as input a list of image URLs that will be processed
- ♥ (optional): `{BASE_URL}/SingleImageUpload/`: An HTTP POST method that provides as input the image itself. This API might prove useful when the module is called from the Mobile App Image module.

The response of the aforementioned APIs is a JSON file/object. It contains the name of the image, the source (i.e. Flickr, Mobile, Webcams), the coordinates of the image, its datetime and its R/G and G/B ratio.

4.1.1 Problem Description

This module's goal is to generate a description of the problem in PDL submitted by the user to the hackAIR platform, according to the information provided by the user via the user interface.

Inputs:

The user query through the system.

Outputs:

The output is PDL description of the user's query.

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java, Apache Jena, OWL.

Architecture:

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

The Problem Description Module gets input from the Personalization Module and converts the query related information (i.e. activity considered, type of request) into RDF statements that will be inserted into the Knowledge Base.

Communication interface:

The communication with the Problem Description Module is realized through REST APIs and is described in the Knowledge Base Module. Specifically using:

- 💡 **{BASE_URL}/InsertData/:** An HTTP POST method that inserts a set of RDF statements to the Knowledge Base. The statements capture information regarding the activity that the user wants to perform and the type of request (answer to a question, decision support, request for a warning).

4.1.2 Recommendations and Decision Support

The decision support module reads the data from the Knowledge Base (which contains the data from the Fusion service, the profile data, and the query data) and using reasoning techniques, it provides recommendations to the end-user.

Inputs:

No input will be used from outside of the system.

Outputs:

The output is the recommendation, which can be an index or value of PM measurement with a recommendation based on the user's profile.

Architecture:

The Recommendation & Decision Support Module gets input from the Knowledge Base Module and after doing some reasoning it provides recommendations to the Personalization Module.

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java, Apache Jena, OWL.

Communication interface:

The communication with the Recommendation & Decision Support Module is realized through REST APIs and is described in the Knowledge Base Module.

4.1.3 Knowledge Base

The Knowledge Base Access Service supports the access to the Knowledge Base on which the whole platform relies to provide user decision support. This service provides, via the KB Access interface, access, manipulation and storage of ontologies (or ontology modules) stored in the Knowledge Base.

Inputs:

Input from other modules (Fusion, Problem Description, Profile Management and Decision Support).

Outputs:

To be defined at later stage.

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Technologies:

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java, Apache Jena, OWL.

Architecture:

The Knowledge Base Module is called by the Profile Management, Data Fusion and Problem Description Modules, in order to get the necessary data from them for responding to a user's query and provide recommendations. The module's architecture is presented in Figure 7

Figure 7: Knowledge base module architecture

Communication interface:

The communication with the Knowledge Base Module is realized through REST APIs. Specifically:

- ♥ `{BASE_URL}/InsertData/`: An HTTP POST method that inserts either of following data into the Knowledge Base as RDF statements, i.e. measurements of interest, the problem described in owl and the user's profile. These data are stored in RDF graphs for each different call/user .
- ♥ `{BASE_URL}/DecisionSupportAndRecommendations/ graph=<graph URI>`: An HTTP GET method that provides as input the graph and provides the recommendations and alerts produced.
- ♥ `{BASE_URL}/DropData/graph=<graph URI>`: An HTTP GET method for deleting the data for the specific graph from the KB.

4.1.4 Data Retrieval

The data retrieval module is responsible for the retrieval of the requested information (i.e. measurements of specific aspects) for the geographical area of interest and time/date.

Inputs:

Query for specific environmental data, time and place.

Outputs:

Environmental measurements related to the query.

Technologies:

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Our current plan for the development of this module includes the following technologies: Java.

Architecture:

The Data Retrieval Module is called by the Text Mining and AQ Estimation Modules, in order to store the air quality values for a given area and timestamp. Then, it provides a set of retrieval functions that allow fetching of relevant data according to the query of the Data Fusion Module and the User Interface. The module's architecture is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Data retrieval module architecture

Communication interface:

The communication with the Data Retrieval Module includes 2 core REST API endpoints. Specifically:

- 📍 (core): `{BASE_URL}/InsertData/`: An HTTP POST method that provides as input the area covered from the measurement, the start/end timestamp, the source and the measurement itself and inserts them in the Database.
- 📍 (core): `{BASE_URL}/SelectData/aspect=<PM10 or PM2.5>×tampStart=<start>×tampEnd=<end>&area=`

`<Geographical Coordinates of point or polygon or circle>&source=<name of the sensor – optional parameter>`: An HTTP GET method that provides as input the name of the pollutant, the start/ end timestamp, the area of interest of the query and the name of the source (optional parameter) and provides a set of measurement responses that match these criteria.

4.1.5 Data Fusion

The fusion module uses geostatistics to combine scattered point-based observations of air quality with spatially exhaustive output from a chemical transport model or a statistical air quality model. Through data fusion, value is added to the observations by spatially interpolating in a mathematically objective fashion, while value is added to the model by constraining it based on the observations.

Inputs:

The module requires qualitative or numerical point observations of aerosol optical depth derived from online- and user-provided photographs as provided by Democritus University and CERTH. If available, up-to-date information from

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

station observations as provided by the EEA can be used to complement this dataset. In addition, the module requires qualitative gridded fields of aerosol optical depth as provided by a chemistry transport model such as those used by the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS).

Outputs:

The module returns qualitative (categorical) maps of aerosol-related air quality (based on particulate matter/aerosol optical depth) that combine the model information with the additional observations derived from the online and user-generated photographs.

Technologies:

The air quality mapping module will be developed in the R programming language.

Architecture:

A draft version of the module's architecture is shown in Figure 9. In summary, the data fusion model takes observations from the hackAIR database as well as modeled maps from the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS), combines these two sources of data and outputs fused maps, which can then further be used by the visualization module to be displayed to the users.

Figure 9: Data fusion architecture

4.1.6 Gamification and Reputation System

The gamification and reputation system module will provide a game-like service to various parts of the application in order for them to allow their end users to gather points, earn badges or rewards as well as provide leaderboards, reputation systems and other user engagement elements. The reputation system part of the module will ensure the quality of data and will minimize risks of capture and manipulation, as competent users will also get motivation from having their contributions being recognized as valuable.

Inputs:

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

The module will require the user's profile information and the user action performed (e.g. image upload, air quality measurement upload, shares to social media etc.).

Outputs:

The module does not have direct outputs, but depending on the case, it could trigger various actions like:

- ♥ addition of points to the user profile
- ♥ addition of points to a user skill (e.g. photography, sky-observer, pollution tracker etc.)
- ♥ earn badges
- ♥ advance in level

Technologies:

The development of this module will include the use of the following technologies: PHP, MySQL.

Architecture:

The module will be called by the web and mobile apps. This communication will be handled through hackAIR's RESTful API. The module will include a security layer in order to validate the requests coming from the client apps before performing any changes to the user's profile. After the request has been validated, the module will make the necessary calls to the database in order to perform the requested action and return the output to the users. The module will use a set of rules in order to determine the action that needs to be performed based on the user's request, for example when a user uploads a new photo to the hackAIR platform, the module may apply a rule that adds a number of points to the user's profile. All actions triggered (addition of points, advance in level etc.) will be logged to the database through a logging mechanism. The architecture of the gamification and reputation system module is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Gamification & Reputation System's architecture

4.2 REST API

The hackAIR platform provides a RESTful API, through which users can perform read, create, update and delete operations on the platform's data using HTTP requests (Wikipedia). The API will be developed using the Laravel framework⁸.

The hackAIR platform RESTful API is presented below:

4.2.1 HTTP Verbs

The HTTP verbs that are currently accepted are the following:

- ♥ GET (read)
- ♥ POST (create)
- ♥ PUT (update)
- ♥ DELETE (delete)

GET and DELETE require no request body.

POST and PUT require the provided data to be encoded in JSON format (application/json) and to be provided in the request body.

4.2.2 HTTP Response Status Codes

Depending on the HTTP verb used in the request, the API may return one of the following HTTP status codes:

Table 1: HTTP response status codes

Response Status Code	Details
200 OK	Successful GET, PUT and DELETE requests will return HTTP status code <code>200 OK</code> and a json encoded response body, if available.
201 Created	Successful POST requests will return HTTP status code <code>201 Created</code> .
400 Bad Request	When the request is invalid (malformed request syntax, invalid request message etc.) a <code>400 Bad Request</code> status code will be returned.
401 Unauthorized	When trying to delete an item the user does not have access to a <code>401 Unauthorized</code> status code will be returned.
404 Not Found	When requesting a resource which ID cannot be found in the database a <code>404 Not Found</code> status code will be returned.
500 Internal Server Error	When the server has encountered an unexpected condition which prevented it from fulfilling the request a <code>500 Internal Server Error</code> status code will be returned.

⁸ <https://laravel.com>

In case of error, the API will include a descriptive error message in the response body, for example:

```
{ "err": "Invalid API key" }
```

4.2.3 Authentication

All requests require token-based authentication headers in order to be able to return information relevant to the current user, using JSON Web Tokens (JWT). Specifically, an HTTP Authorization header should be included to the request, for example:

```
Authorization: Bearer QWxhZGRpbjpvYVUHNlc2FtZQ==
```

In specific methods authorization is optional or not required. For example, creating a new user requires no authentication.

4.2.4 Endpoints

The main endpoints of the API are listed here:

Users:

- ♥ GET /users **Retrieves a list of users.**
- ♥ GET /users/{userId} **Retrieves a specific user.**
- ♥ POST /users **Creates a new user.**
- ♥ PUT /users/{userId} **Updates a specific user.**
- ♥ DELETE /users/{userId} **Deletes a specific user.**

Sensors

- ♥ GET /sensors?userId={userId} **Retrieves a list of sensors for a specific user.**
- ♥ POST /sensors **Creates a new sensor.**
- ♥ PUT /sensors/{sensorId} **Updates a sensor.**
- ♥ DELETE /sensors/{sensorId} **Deletes an existing sensor.**

Photos:

- ♥ GET /photos **Retrieves a list of photos.**
- ♥ GET /photos?userId={userId} **Retrieves a list of photos for a specific user.**
- ♥ POST /photos **Creates a new photo.**
- ♥ DELETE /photos/{photoId} **Deletes an existing photo.**

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Measurements:

- ♥ GET /measurements?from={locationFrom}&to={locationTo} **Retrieves a list of measurements in a specific geographical rectangular area. Optional parameters: type (e.g. user-images to retrieve images uploaded by the users of the mobile app).**
- ♥ POST /measurements **Creates a new measurement.**

5 Software & Hardware Specifications

This section presents our decisions regarding the specifications for the installation and successful operation of the hackAIR platform so far. It is just a first assessment of the hardware and software requirements and we will regularly review this list in order to make sure we always use the most appropriate technologies for the development of hackAIR.

5.1 Hardware Specifications

In terms of hardware, the hackAIR platform requires two web servers in order to operate successfully, one running the Linux operating system and one running Windows. These servers have the following requirements:

Linux web server:

- ♥ **Graphics card: Nvidia (e.g. GeForce GTX TITAN X, Tesla K40 GPU Accelerator)**
- ♥ **Processor: 3.5GHz CPU, dual-core minimum**
- ♥ **Memory: 16 GB RAM minimum, 32 GB recommended**
- ♥ **Disc space: 1GB minimum**

Windows web server:

- ♥ **Graphics card: Nvidia (e.g. GeForce GTX 650)**
- ♥ **Processor: 3.5GHz CPU, dual-core minimum**
- ♥ **Memory: 16 GB RAM minimum, 32 GB recommended**
- ♥ **Disc space: 1GB minimum**

5.2 Software Specifications

The software requirements of the hackAIR platform and its subcomponents are listed below. The two web servers required to host the platform need to run the Linux and Windows operating systems.

For the Linux web server, there are the following minimum software requirements:

- ♥ **Apache Web server 2.4 or later, with the following modules enabled:**
 - Headers
 - Rewrite
- ♥ **PHP version 5.5.9 or later, with the following extensions enabled:**
 - OpenSSL
 - PDO
 - Mbstring
 - Tokenizer

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

- ♥ The R programming language⁹ (version 3.3 or later) with various packages installed including: raster, sp, gstat, automap, ncdf4, and others.
- ♥ An operational FTP server (either anonymous/public or with account) so that the Copernicus services at <http://www.regional.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/> can use FTP-push to upload the latest CAMS data onto the hackAir server.
- ♥ CUDA (software for parallel programming created by NVIDIA)
- ♥ MongoDB
- ♥ Apache Jena
- ♥ Apache Jena Fuseki Server
- ♥ Apache Nutch

For the Windows web server:

- ♥ CUDA (software for parallel programming created by NVIDIA)
- ♥ Apache Tomcat server 7.x
- ♥ PostgreSQL

6 hackAIR Implementation Approach

6.1 Software Development Methodology

We will be using an agile approach to the software development. Agile methodologies help businesses respond quickly to changing requirements. It promotes adaptive planning, evolutionary development and delivery, a time-boxed iterative approach, and encourages rapid and flexible response to change. One of the most widely used system development frameworks, based on the agile methodology, is Scrum which is the one we will be using.

Scrum

Scrum¹⁰ is a management framework for incremental product development using one or more cross-functional, self-organizing teams. It provides a structure of roles, meetings, rules, and artifacts. Teams are responsible for creating and adapting their processes within this framework. Scrum uses fixed-length iterations, called Sprints, which are typically two weeks to 30 days long. Scrum teams attempt to build a potentially shippable (properly tested) product increment on every iteration.

⁹ <https://www.r-project.org>

¹⁰ <http://scrumreferencecard.com/scrum-reference-card/>

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Figure 11: Scrum in a picture¹¹

Our approach

The requirements were transformed in the form of User Stories (US). A User Story is describing in simple language a requirement at a very high level. It contains the right amount of information for the team to be able to estimate the effort needed to implement it. A first set of user stories can be found in APPENDIX I.

The list of user stories forms the product backlog (aka the list of all things that need to be completed as part of the project). For a more effective implementation, we will prioritize the backlog based on the input we had from the user requirements as well as the dependencies between the stories (for example US3 can only be worked if US1 is done). Responsible for the prioritization is the product owner.

A story is described as **DONE** only when:

- ♥ **Development is complete**
- ♥ **Testing has taken place**
- ♥ **All bugs are fixed**
- ♥ **Product owner has approved the story**

Once the product backlog is in the right order the team together with the product owner will estimate the effort needed for each US. The unit of estimation will be pseudo Fibonacci numbers.

We will run two week sprints and we will release to the production once a month. Should the need arise, we might release sooner. At the beginning of the sprint, the team will commit to the stories that will be completed within the two week period and discuss the details of the stories, fleshing out the technical details in order to form the acceptance criteria and break the story down in smaller tasks.

During our daily stand up, we will be reviewing the progress of the stories and mention any problems that may risk the completion of the committed work.

At the end of each sprint/release we will have a potentially shippable product. A retrospective meeting will take place to discuss what went well, what could have gone better and what we would change in the next sprint.

¹¹ <http://scrumreferencecard.com/scrum-reference-card/>

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

Before every release we would run some regression tests to make sure that nothing is broken to the previously developed features.

After each release (and only if there is something tangible to show) we will be holding webinars so that all partners of the consortium can get updated on the latest new features.

The progress of the team will be tracked with the use of a burndown chart¹².

6.2 Technical Documentation Management

For the creation of the technical documentation for the hackAIR platform API we will use Swagger¹³, a widely known framework for describing an API using a common language, allowing the API's consumers to discover and understand the capabilities of the service without access to source code, documentation, or through network traffic inspection.

Swagger describes the specifications that developers need to follow in order to describe their code, providing all necessary information (endpoints, http verbs, request parameters etc.) and provides tools to generate a visual documentation of the API based on these descriptions, that makes it easy for other developers to understand and test the API. A sample documentation created using Swagger is shown in *Figure 12: Swagger UI*

Figure 12: Swagger UI

Figure 12: Swagger UI

6.3 Source Code Repository Management

The hackAIR platform will be open source, allowing developers to install, customize and extend it. Thus, we will use GitHub as a source code repository for all components of the platform. The main project repository will be available on Github at the following address:

¹² <https://www.mountangoatsoftware.com/agile/scrum/release-burndown>

¹³ <http://swagger.io/>

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

<https://github.com/hackair-project>

Under the main project repository there will be a separate repository for each of the platform's subcomponents, for example:

- ♥ <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-web> the hackAIR website
- ♥ <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-mobile> the hackAIR mobile app
- ♥ <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-api> the hackAIR API

6.4 Issue Tracking Management & Reporting

Taiga¹⁴ will be used as an issue tracking tool during the development of the hackAIR platform. Taiga is an open source, cloud project management tool for agile development. It is free for public projects that are discoverable through the taiga platform. By using Taiga we have the advantage of centralizing user stories and issues in one common place. Using Taiga, we can effectively organize our work in sprints.

6.5 Deployment Methodology

For the deployment of the hackAIR platform, we will use the Continuous Integration (CI)¹⁵ approach, a development practice that requires developers to integrate code into a shared repository several times a day. Each check-in is then verified by an automated build, allowing teams to detect problems early. This approach will allow us to detect errors quickly, and locate them more easily.

As part of the deployment methodology we will use Docker¹⁶, a software technology for deploying applications inside lightweight containers. This allows the overall system to manage and start components as required and is more effective in terms of resources as the containers do not require the full resources of a virtual or physical machine but can provide the functionality required. This allows the software components to be turned into deployable micro-services.

7 Testing Methodology

7.1 Testing Methodology

In this section we describe the testing methodology that will be adopted during the development of the hackAIR platform. The purpose of the testing stage is to verify and validate the platform from the very low level technical details all the way to the User Interface. Different types of testing will be performed throughout the development of the platform and these are described in the sections below.

The testing methodology will be updated accordingly for the duration of the project and any specific testing requirements and considerations will be taken into consideration as they come along.

Towards the end of each sprint and based on the estimation of the US included in the sprint, there will be a specific amount of time allocated for testing. The stories will be tested based on the acceptance criteria that are defined within

¹⁴ <https://taiga.io/>

¹⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Continuous_integration

¹⁶ <https://www.docker.com/>

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

the US and the list of requirements. The person responsible for testing each batch of stories will be involved in all the procedures related to story writing and elaboration for a specific sprint. Any bugs found as part of this exercise will be logged in our issue tracking system and will be fixed before the end of the sprint if possible. The decision about whether a bug can slip to another sprint will be taken in coordination of the developer, the tester and the product owner based on the severity and the impact of the bug. Once all bugs are fixed, a final overview of the delivered functionality will take place to verify we are ready to go. As mentioned above, if the current sprint is a release sprint at the end of it we will run a round of regression tests to ensure we have no broken functionality.

At this stage all the changes will be moved from the internal testing server to the staging server so that partners can have access to all the new features developed as part of the last 2 sprints. Partners will have the opportunity to give us feedback in the form of issues within Taiga which will be taken into consideration and be prioritized accordingly.

7.2 API & Integration Testing

The REST API handles the communication between the various modules of the hackAIR platform and therefore needs to be tested in order to ensure its successful operation. For this reason we will test the API's endpoints by sending requests with specific parameters and making sure that proper data and status codes are returned in the response.

After each component is ready, we will integrate it into the hackAIR platform and perform integration testing by passing the necessary inputs to the component and validating that it produces the expected outputs. We will ensure the communication between the "new component" and the remaining system works as expected and that if the specific module is not working, the system will not fail as a whole.

7.3 User Interface Testing

The hackAIR application will be tested in the latest versions of all common browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, IE, Mobile browsers) in order to ensure that the look and feel experience will be the same for all users no matter what browser they are using.

7.4 Security Testing

Security is considered of high importance and we will make sure the hackAIR platform will be secure and protected from malicious attacks. In section 3.1.3 we describe in details the security threats that we deal with and what we will do in order to stay protected.

7.5 User Acceptance Testing (UAT)

User Acceptance testing will be performed by the partners who are responsible for the pilots (BUND NILU), and will verify that the platform was developed according to the requirements. As described above, functionality will be delivered in iterations and partners will be able to give us feedback through Taiga.

8 Conclusions

This document describes the general architecture of the hackAIR platform, its components and implementation approach, lists all the tools that will be used for the development of the platform, provides general architectural guidelines for UI design, localization, security and testing and lists all the software and hardware requirements. Furthermore, this document provides a high level description of the API end points that will be developed.

Our main target audience is the technical partners of the consortium in order to get a good understanding of the hackAIR architecture and integration framework.

This deliverable will act as a reference for the technical partners during the development and the evaluation of the platform and as an information source for all the partners of the hackAIR consortium.

References

REpresentational State Transfer. (2016). Retrieved from Wikipedia:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer

Appendix I – List of User stories

The following list of user stories is not an exhaustive one. There is a great chance that as we proceed to the development phase we will create new user stories and amend the existing ones. The user stories with the word [EPIC] in the front are very generic, big user stories that will have to be broken down to smaller ones when we elaborate them. Lastly, the stories are not prioritized.

Registration/ login

As a user I want to be able to register to the hackAIR platform only by providing the username and password (web and mobile). The rest should be optional.

As a user I want to have the opportunity to give personal information about myself during registration.

As a user I should be able to register through social media

As a user who has been registered with hackAIR I want to be able to login in to the hackAIR platform.

As a user I should be able to login through social media

As a user I want to have a forgot my password option

As a user I want to be able to sign out

AQ information

[EPIC] As a user I want to have access to educational information about AQ

As a user who does not want to register to the hackAIR application I should be able to have access to some **basic** AQ information.

As a user I want to see the AQ information about my city using colors and numerical scales

As a user I want to see a map displaying AQ in my city (web and mobile)

As a user I want to know where the data come from (sources)

As a user I want to be able to check the AQ of another city

As a user I want to be able to compare the AQ in my city to that of other cities

As a user I want to be able to have access to historical data about AQ and see how this has changed over time

As a user I want to have the ability to inform my friends about the AQ of a city.

As a user I want to be given **actionable** advice on how to reduce air pollution

As a user I want to receive advice on how to avoid air pollution

As a user I want to be told which activities I should be doing or not on a specific day

As a user I want to be able to share advices with my friends

As a user I am able to see other user's contributions and impact on improving AQ.

Mobile

[EPIC] As a user I want a mobile application (iOS and Android)

[EPIC] As a user I want a tablet application (iOS and Android)

As a user I want to receive push notifications on my mobile

As an Android user I want to easily discover and download the app from the play store

As an iPhone user I want to easily discover and download the app from the AppStore/iTunes.

[Placeholder/ note] As a user accessing the website from my mobile web browser I want to have the same unique experience like using the Android/iOS app.

Gamification

As a user I can earn points by doing specific activities/tasks. As a result I will be more recognized among other users My points and my recognition status are visible in my accounts profile and given my permission other people can have access to it.

As a user I am able to see my ranking compared to everyone else

As a user I can check my ranking compared to that of my friends

As a user I can check my ranking compared to that of people that are nearby

D5.1: Architecture and Integration Framework Definition Specification

As a user interested in keeping up in the ranks I want to receive a notification when my rank drops

Social

As a user I want to be able to discover hackAIR users around me

As a user I want to be able to connect with users around me

As a user I can see who of my friends from social media are using hackAIR and I can connect with them in hackAIR

[Epic] As a user I want to have a tool to help me communicate with other users by asking questions, giving answers etc

Notifications

As a user I can configure the notifications I receive based on importance, type etc.

As a user I want to receive sms notifications

As a user I want to receive email notifications

As a user I should be able to unsubscribe from email/sms notifications

As a user I want to receive notifications regarding the impact my activities have on improving AQ.

As a user I want to receive notifications regarding the AQ of the area I live in.

Photos

As user very eager to contribute to AQ measurements, I want to be able to upload photos through the hackAIR mobile app that will be used to calculate air pollution. (linked to R6)

As a user I want clear guidelines on how I should on how to take the pictures (filters, angle, proportion of sky)

The hackAIR app must save the photos in the database along with the geolocation and the time the photo was taken.

Sensors

As a user I want to be given instruction on how to build my own air quality sensors

[EPIC] As a user that has built an AQ sensor, I want my data to be send to the hackAIR app and be taken into account when calculating air pollution

As a hackAIR admin, I want the sensor measurements to be timestamped and geotagged

Others

As a user, I want to be able to add personal information about myself through the “my profile” area of the hackAIR app.

As a user I want to amend my preferences through the “my profile” area of the hackAIR app.

As a user I should be able to report my perception of the atmosphere by entering a rating on the air quality for a specific location

As a user I would like to know how the perceived quality relates to the actual AQ

As an eager contributor, I want to know in which areas there is a lack of measurements so that I can contribute

As a user I want to know the level of my contribution (i.e. you contributed 35% of the local measurements)

As a user I want feedback on the quality of the data I sent

[EPIC] As an environmentalist who is responsible for the AQ information of the hackAIR, I want to control the measurements that enter our pool and remove outliers and errors.

As a non-English speaking user I want to view the website translated in my language (localization).

As a hackAIR administrator I want to make sure users are aware that their personal data are secure and private.

As a hackAIR developer I want to have access to the hackAIR code and receive clear instructions about the different parts of the system

As someone who is interested in installing hackAIR as a community portal, I want to receive clear instructions on how to run this process.

